

D6.3 – Project Flyer

prepared for

WP6.2 – Material for dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

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Table of contents

Table of contents 3

Acronyms.....4

1 REPORT SUMMARY / INTRODUCTION.....5

2 LUWEX PROJECT FLYER.....6

3 CONCLUSION.....9

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
LUWEX	Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies		
AI	Artificial Intelligence		
CE	Concurrent Engineering		
ISRU	In-Situ Resource Utilisation		

1 REPORT SUMMARY / INTRODUCTION

The successful completion of EU initiatives depends heavily on the dissemination and exploitation of project progress and results. The members of the LUWEX team work together to complete tasks in this direction.

Dissemination and exploitation fall under work package 6, which is made up of several communication-related tasks for a variety of stakeholders (including the scientific community, policymakers, business, the general public, educators, and students). This report will present the LUWEX project flyer.

The goal of project LUWEX is to create the impact required to demonstrate that LUWEX is significantly influencing the European space exploration and space resources field. To achieve this the project flyer is one material out of many that has been successfully distributed at the 2023 Space Resources conference in Luxembourg.

2 LUXWEX PROJECT FLYER

As give-away the team developed a LUXWEX project flyer with very concise information about the project. On the outer page the taglines and a two-sentence project description are found, the partners logos and the reference to EU funding and the grant agreement number (see Figure 1). The folded title page just shows one for the key images and the project title serving as a small poster/postcard. The design team intended to create a small “poster” from the unfolded front/outer page so people would pin it to their office walls or at home to have LUXWEX always visible.

Figure 1: LUXWEX project flyer front/outer page

The inner side of the flyer reveals more information on ISRU in general, the project’s objectives, and the expected outcomes and result. All is graphically enhanced so it becomes enticing in form and easy to read (see Figure 2).

Figure 3 shows the folding process and how the information can be accessed.

Sustainable space exploration requires the development of In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) technologies.

ISRU encompasses all processes, which utilize locally available resources to generate products and that can be used for robotic and human exploration. Local resources include water, volatiles, metals, rocks, regolith, atmospheric constituents, and also includes waste products such as human trash and discarded hardware components.

ISRU systems greatly decrease the required resupply from Earth and will enable humanity to establish a permanent presence on the Moon, on Mars and in other locations of the solar system.

Of all the natural resources, water is, by far, the most versatile and most needed resource in space exploration.

- PROJECT OBJECTIVES:**
- (1) Development of water extraction, purification, and quality monitoring technologies for an in-situ raw water process chain;
 - (2) Designing and manufacturing an integrated validation test setup to provide a proper test environment as an essential preparatory activity for future space exploration;
 - (3) Validation of in-situ raw water technologies in an integrated test setup in a laboratory environment;
 - (4) Advancing the European excellence in space exploration by developing and validating leading edge in-situ resource utilization technologies;
 - (5) Improving the interdisciplinary collaboration and leveraging synergies of industry, academia and institutional research within Europe.

Water is the substance with the highest daily demand in human spaceflight. It can be stored and directly used as consumable for astronauts. Water can also be used as a radiation absorbing material to provide protection for astronauts.

Additionally, water can be decomposed to hydrogen and oxygen using electrolysis.

PROJECT RESULTS
Project execution (2022-2024)

- Laboratory breadboard and validation of a lunar water extraction, purification and quality monitoring.
- Lunar raw water simulant and a lunar ice-dust simulant for scientific experiments.
- Provision of scientific data from the technology validation experiments.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES
Medium-term effects (2024+)

- Lunar water extractor and purifier as contribution to European-led space exploration of the Moon.
- Validation of the ISRU water process chain in an analogue environment.
- Simulants, data and strategies for science and leading-edge technology developments in Europe.

EXPECTED IMPACT
Long-term effects (2030)

- Demonstration on the Moon of European capabilities to exploit lunar water ice deposits.
- European, disruptive ISRU technologies enabling new innovations and business cases.
- Enabling excellent science activities in Europe for lunar exploration and science.

Figure 2:LUWEX project flyer back/inner page

Figure 3:LUWEX project flyer back/inner page

The flyer is also stored on the website and can be accessed via <https://luwex.space/category/publications/> (see Fig.4)

The screenshot shows the LUWEX website navigation menu with links for NEWS, PROJECT, GALLERIES, PODCASTS, PUBLICATIONS, PARTNERS, and CONTACT. A circular logo with the text 'LUWEX' and a moon graphic is positioned in the top left. The main content area features two articles:

- APRIL 13, 2023**: A project flyer titled "Water is the driving force of all nature". The flyer image shows a lunar landscape with a small structure. Below the image is a "Project flyer" section with a "Click here to download" link and a "Detailed Information" link.
- NOVEMBER 15, 2022**: A press release titled "WATER ON THE MOON". The press release image shows two circular diagrams. Below the image is a "Press release 1" section with a "Click here to download" link and a "Detailed Information" link.

At the bottom of the website, there is a row of partner logos: DLR (Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt German Aerospace Center), Technische Universität Braunschweig, LIQUIFER SYSTEMS GROUP, ThalesAlenia Space, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, and Scanway imaging space. Below the logos, a dark teal banner contains the text: "LUWEX HAS BEEN FUNDED UNDER THE GRANT AGREEMENT NO. 101081937 – HORIZON 2022 - SPACE SCIENCE AND EXPLORATION TECHNOLOGIES" and "© 2023 - LUWEX - IMPRINT / PRIVACY NOTE". A circular logo with the text 'LUWEX' and a moon graphic is positioned in the bottom right of the banner.

Figure 4: LUWEX project flyer downloadable on the website

3 CONCLUSION

Dissemination and Exploitation efforts are of critical importance for sharing knowledge of project developments and achievements. The LUWEX project flyer was conceived as a give-away at conference, fairs and any other public events.

